

THREE-DIMENSIONAL GRAPHENE FOAM/CNT/PDMS COMPOSITES WITH EXCEPTIONAL MICROWAVE AND NOISE SHIELDING

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ABSTRACT

Graphene foams (GFs) with a cellular structure are prepared based on a chemical vapour deposition (CVD) method. They possess unique properties, such as very low densities, excellent electrical conductivities, and high elasticity and flexibility. GF/poly(dimethyl siloxane) (PDMS) composites are fabricated by incorporating solvent-diluted PDMS into the porous GFs. The unique three-dimensional interconnected porous structure of the composites with inherent percolation can find multi-functional applications requiring electromagnetic wave and sound wave absorption. The GF/PDMS composite with a 90.8% porosity shows the highest electrical conductivity of 6.74 S/cm, leading to the highest EMI SE of average 25 dB in the X-band frequency; while the composite containing a 51.5% porosity is the best performer in terms of sound absorption coefficient in the low frequency 100-1000 Hz. These properties are further enhanced by introducing well-dispersed multi-walled carbon nanotubes (MWCNTs) in the PDMS matrix to form a hybrid structure with two different scales of electrically conductive, open channels. The hybrid composites display significant enhancements in both EMI shielding performance and low frequency sound absorption, compared to the GF/PDMS composites. The GF/MWCNT/PDMS composite with 2 wt.% CNTs and 90.8% porosity delivers an excellent electrical conductivity of 31.5 S/cm and a remarkable EMI SE of ~75 dB, equivalent to nearly 200% increment against the GF/PDMS composite with the same porosity. The addition of MWCNTs significantly improves the overall sound energy dissipation by friction between the CNTs and polymer matrix, leading to a commercially viable sound absorption coefficient of more than 0.3 over the frequency range 100-1000Hz.

1 INTRODUCTION

Electromagnetic interference (EMI) has drawn much attention in recent years due to rapidly increasing electromagnetic pollution caused by the proliferation of telecommunication and mobile electronic devices. Traditional metal-based EMI shielding materials have many weaknesses, such as high densities, susceptibility to corrosion, poor flexibility and processing difficulties [1]. Low density and high EMI shielding effectiveness are two principal criteria for the next-generation EMI shielding materials, and lightweight is particularly important in space applications [2]. Consequently, nanocarbon materials including carbon nanotubes (CNTs) [3-7] and graphene [8-10], have been regarded a potential replacement for metallic shielding materials due to their high electrical conductivities, large specific surface areas and low densities. Electrically conducting polymer composites reinforced with carbon fillers are also widely investigated. In particular, CNT/graphene/polymer hybrid nanocomposites were fabricated to achieve synergies from each of the EMI shielding materials [11-13]. However, there are two major reasons for all these hybrid composites

to present limited EMI shielding performance: namely, (i) the composites lacked internal channels for microwave dissipation because they were in the form of fully integrated, compact solids; and (ii) conducting networks were absent, thus displaying low electrical conductivities. Judging from these mechanisms, materials with a foam structure are an attractive choice because they provide more paths for energy attenuation by multiple reflections of electromagnetic waves. A new 3D graphene foam (GF)/PDMS composite with a low graphene content of ~0.8 wt.% has been reported to display an excellent EMI SE of 20 dB in the X-band frequency range due to the inherently interconnected, conductive GF structure [14]. However, the influence of material porosity on SE and the underlying shielding mechanisms have not been specifically studied, and the shielding performance needs further improvement for practical applications.

Sound damping is also of practical importance due to the serious noise pollution problems in recent years. Four mechanisms are important for materials, especially polymers, to damp vibration and absorb sound in view of their viscoelastic nature: namely, (i) mode conversion at boundaries, (ii) scattering by inhomogeneities, (iii) redirection, and (iv) intrinsic absorption by conversion to heat [15]. As a consequence, a solid viscoelastic material is inefficient in sound absorption, whereas open-cell porous materials are widely applied since they can allow the sound waves to enter into the channels, reverberate and finally dissipate or become absorbed. Inclusions like microcells or large voids may also help sound energy attenuation by scattering or converting incidental, longitudinal waves to other modes of wave propagation. Carbon materials, including graphitic foams, showed a promising potential for sound damping because of their lightweight and excellent sound absorption properties [16]. Although most commercial sound-absorbing foams perform excellent at high frequencies, the attenuation of low-frequency sounds below 1000 Hz has always been a big challenge because the intrinsic dissipation of materials is weak in this regime [17]. Micro-perforated panel (MPP) absorbers have been widely investigated due to their low-frequency sound absorption capabilities, but they have a critical drawback of relatively narrow sound absorption bandwidths near their respective resonance frequencies. Therefore, a sound absorber with holes drilled in multiple sizes was proposed to possess wider absorbing frequency band [18].

This paper reports the multi-functionalities of GF/CNT/PDMS hybrid composites with different porosities, densities and CNT contents. Compared to the neat PDMS foams or GF/PDMS composites, the hybrid structure with two different scales of highly conductive carbons with open channels yields significant enhancements in absorption of both microwaves and low-frequency sounds. The mechanisms behind the excellent shielding performance of the composites are specifically evaluated.

2 EXPERIMENTAL

2.1 Fabrication of GF/PDMS and GF/CNT/PDMS composites

Ni foams of 1.6 mm in thickness and 320 g/m² in areal density (Heze Tianyu Technology Development) were used as the template for chemical vapour deposition (CVD), similar to our previous work [19]. The 60 mm × 90 mm rectangular Ni foam pieces were placed in the quartz tube, and the temperature was raised to 1000 °C under Ar and H₂ flow and maintained for 10 min for annealing. The carbon precursor CH₄ was introduced into the tube for 10 min. The furnace was then rapidly cooled to ambient after stopping the CH₄ supply. Gas flows of 500, 200 and 15 sccm (for 1.4vol.% CH₄) were chosen for Ar, H₂ and CH₄, respectively.

To prepare matrix precursors with different PDMS contents and viscosities, PDMS (Sylgard184, Dow Corning, base agent/curing agent = 10/1 by weight) was diluted with ethyl acetate solvent at different base agent/curing agent/solvent ratios ranging from 10/1/0 to 10/1/100. The liquid polymer was deposited onto the graphene/Ni foam, and cured at 80 °C for 2 h in an oven while the solvent was evaporated. The nickel skeleton was etched by HCl (3M) afterwards at 60 °C for 12 h and rinsed by DI water to obtain the GF/PDMS composites. Neat PDMS foams were also fabricated as a control group by depositing the liquid polymer onto the bare Ni foam followed by Ni etching.

MWCNTs (supplied by NanoKarbon Co. with outer diameters 60-80 nm and lengths ~20µm) [20] were cleaned by ultrasonication in DI water and treated by UV/O₃ for 2 h to create oxygenated functional groups on their surfaces. The functionalized MWCNTs were dispersed in ethyl acetate by

ultrasonication for 1 h, which were mixed with PDMS base polymer and curing agent while stirring and ultrasonication. The mixture was applied onto the graphene/Ni foam followed by curing and etching, similarly to the above process, to obtain the GF/MWCNT/PDMS hybrid composites.

2.2 Characterization and measurements of EMI SEs and sound absorption coefficients

The morphologies of the composites were characterized by scanning electron microscopy (SEM, JEOL JES-6700F and 7100F). A resistivity/Hall measurement system (Scientific Equipment & Services) was used to measure the electrical conductivities based on the four-point probe method. The graphene concentration in wt.% in the composites was measured from the known weight of GF and the final composites (which varied with matrix content).

The porosities, ε , of the composites were calculated by equation (1) [21]:

$$\varepsilon = \left(1 - \frac{\rho_a}{\rho_t}\right) \times 100\% \quad (1)$$

where ρ_a is the apparent density and ρ_t is the true density of the composites. The microwave scattering parameters, S_{11} and S_{12} , of the composites in the frequency range of 8.2-12.4 GHz were measured on a vector network analyzer (VNA, MS2038C, Anritsu) connected with waveguide tubes (WR-90, Agilent). The total EMI shielding effectiveness, SE_T , as well as the shielding effectiveness by reflection and absorption, SE_R and SE_A , were determined according to the scattering parameters [22]:

$$SE_T = 10 \log (P_I/P_T) \quad (2)$$

$$SE_R = -10 \log (1 - R) \quad (3)$$

$$SE_A = -10 \log (T/(1 - R)) \quad (3)$$

$$SE_T = SE_R + SE_A \quad (4)$$

where P_I and P_T are the powers of incident wave and transmitted wave, respectively. R and T are the power ratios of reflected to incident waves, and transmitted to incident waves, respectively. Thus, R corresponds to the normalized power reflected back at port 1, whereas T is related to the normalized power transmitted from port 1 to port 2 through the device. The sound absorption coefficients, α , were measured on an impedance tube apparatus consisting of two Bruel & Kjaer Type-4206 impedance tubes with the samples placed in between. The absorption coefficient is given by equation (5) [23]:

$$\alpha = 1 - |r|^2 + |t|^2 \quad (5)$$

where r and t are measured reflection and transmission coefficients, respectively.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 GF and GF/PDMS composites

Figure 1: SEM images of GF/PDMS composites with porosities of (a) 9.3%; (b) 28.9%; (c) 51.5%; (d) 73.2%; (e) 90.8% and (f) pure GF without PDMS coating.

The as-synthesized GF contained 4-7 graphene layers and displayed an electrical conductivity of 7.2 S/cm, with a BET specific surface area of over 200 m²/g. The essential parameters and the physical properties of the GF/PDMS composites are given in Table 1 and the corresponding SEM morphologies are presented in Figure 1. Different solvent contents were added to a given weight of PDMS base/curing agent, leading to different matrix contents as well as different densities and porosities of the composites. The composites made from the weight ratio of 10/1/0 without solvent showed an almost full solid structure with only 3D interconnected GF channels (Figure 1(a)). The density of the composite, 0.88 g/cm³, was slightly lower than 0.965 g/cm³ of solid PDMS because of the pores present within the graphene foam skeleton. The density of the composite decreased with increasing solvent content in the matrix mixture, while the corresponding porosity and graphene concentration increased. Thus, the composites fabricated with the most diluted PDMS solution (with a ratio of 10/1/100) had a high porosity of 90.8%, while maintaining the pristine graphene foam structure with a very thin PDMS coating (Figure 1(e)). Figure 1(f) shows the morphology of GF without PDMS, very similar to the previous studies [19, 24].

GF/PDMS composites	PDMS base/curing agent/solvent weight ratio				
	10/1/0	10/1/1	10/1/10	10/1/50	10/1/100
Graphene concentration (wt.%)	0.28	0.36	0.53	0.96	2.7
Apparent density, ρ_a (g/cm ³)	0.88	0.69	0.47	0.26	0.09
True density, ρ_t (g/cm ³)	0.97	0.97	0.97	0.97	0.98
Porosity, ε (%)	9.3	28.9	51.5	73.2	90.8
Electrical conductivity (S/cm)	1.13	1.80	4.01	4.96	6.74

Table 1: Graphene concentrations, apparent densities, porosities and electrical conductivities of

GF/PDMS composites prepared at different PDMS base/curing agent/solvent weight ratios.

3.2 Electrical properties and EMI shielding effectiveness

Figure 2(a) and Table 1 present the electrical conductivities of the GF/PDMS composites. The conductivity increased with increasing graphene concentration, or when the porosity increased. For example, the change in porosity from 9.3% to 90.8% resulted in a six-fold increase in conductivity. EMI shielding has three major mechanisms [25]: (i) reflection from the material/structure surface, (ii) microwave absorption and (iii) multiple reflections within the material, which can be neglected when the total shielding effectiveness, SE_T , is higher than 15 dB [12, 14]. Both excellent electrical conductivities and high porosities are essential to high EMI SEs. From Figure 2(d), it is clear that with increasing porosity, both the SE values due to reflection and absorption mechanisms increased. For the GF/PDMS composites, SE_A contributed more significantly to the total effectiveness, SE_T , than SE_R because of both the high conductivity and the large number of internal channels for wave dissipation. As a result, SE_{Ts} showed an increasing trend with increasing porosity, and the GF/PDMS composite with 90.8% porosity exhibited the highest EMI shielding performance with an average of 25 dB (Figure 2(b)).

Figure 2: (a) Electrical conductivities of GF/PDMS and GF/CNT/PDMS composites; SE_T of (b) GF/PDMS composites with different porosities and (c) GF/CNT/PDMS composites with different CNT contents as a function of frequency; Comparison of average values of SE_T , SE_A and SE_R over the whole frequency range of (d) GF/PDMS composites with different porosities and (e) GF/CNT/PDMS composites with different CNT contents.

However, the SE of GF/PDMS composite with 90.8% porosity was limited by the low electrical conductivity and the absence of optimized structure, therefore oxygen-functionalized MWCNTs were incorporated into the composite with the same porosity. There was a substantial enhancement in electrical conductivity of the hybrid composites, seeing Figure 2(a), due to the presence of CNTs in the interconnected GF/PDMS composites. With a CNT content 2 wt.%, the electrical conductivity of the hybrid composites approached 31.5 S/cm, corresponding to over 350% surge compared to the GF/PDMS composites. However, the conductivity of the composites with 5 wt.% CNTs did not follow the same increasing trend probably owing to heavy agglomeration at high filler contents [26, 27]. Much enhanced EMI SEs of the hybrid composites due to CNTs are shown in Figures 2(c). SE_T consistently enhanced with increasing CNT content, where the microwave absorption by CNTs, SE_A , played an important role (Figure 2(e)). Meanwhile, the reflection component, SE_R , remained almost unchanged regardless of CNT content since the interconnected structure did not change. It is worth noting that SE_T of the GF/CNT/PDMS composite with 2 wt.% CNTs increased to an average of 75 dB by almost 200% compared to the GF/PDMS composite. Further increase in CNT content to 5 wt.%, nevertheless, did not present a proportional improvement in shielding performance, indicating little contribution by the agglomerated CNTs to microwave absorption of the composites [3].

Figure 3: (a) Schematic illustration of effective EMI shielding by GF/CNT/PDMS composites; (b) GF-based composites with GF framework decorated with well-dispersed CNTs and an uniform thin coating layer of PDMS; (c) hollow microscale GF and (d) nanoscale CNT channels that effectively reflect and absorb the electromagnetic waves.

Figure 3 summarizes the mechanisms of effective EMI shielding of the composites using a schematic illustration of the GF/CNT/PDMS hybrid structure. The incident microwave was either reflected on the surface or absorbed by the electrically conductive channels by the interconnected microscale GF. Meanwhile, the myriad CNTs embedded in the polymer forced the microwaves to be dissipated and attenuated through their nanoscale channels by multiple scattering and interfacial electric polarization. The defects in UV/O₃ functionalized CNTs [7], as well as a large density of the interface between the CNTs and polymer matrix [3] favor the interfacial electrical polarization.

The specific EMI SEs were calculated by dividing absolute SEs by the densities of the materials and are compared among different composites made from various carbon fillers, as shown in Table 2 [28-35]. The current GF/CNT/PDMS hybrid composites displayed exceptional SEs compared to the other types of composites: their absolute and specific EMI SEs approached remarkable 75 dB and 833 dB cm³/g with 2.7 wt.% GF and 2.0 wt.% CNTs. The extremely low density of the hybrid composites, 0.09 g/cm³ (Table 1), led to the exceptionally high specific SE value, which is particularly attractive for aerospace applications.

Material	Filler content	EMI SE (dB)	Specific EMI SE (dB cm ³ /g)	Reference
Copper	-	90.2	10.1	[28]
CNT/PS foam	7 wt.%	~19	33	[29]

Ordered mesoporous carbon/fused silica	10 vol.%	~40	-	[30]
Carbon black/carbon fiber	-	~50	-	[31]
Graphene/epoxy	15 wt.%	21	-	[32]
Graphene/PMMA foam	1.8 vol.%	19	25	[33]
CNT/ABS	15 wt.%	~50	-	[34]
GF/PDMS foam	0.8 wt.%	30	500	[14]
CNT/graphene/PDMS	10 wt.%	10	<10	[11]
rGO/epoxy	2 wt.%	38	35.3	[35]
GF/CNT/PDMS	2.7 wt.% GF/ 2 wt.% CNT	75	833	Current work

Table 2: Comparison of absolute EMI SEs and specific EMI SEs with different carbon-based materials

3.3 Sound absorption

Figure 4: (a) Effect of porosity on sound absorption coefficient, α , of GF/PDMS composites; (b) comparison of α between neat PDMS foams and GF/PDMS composites both with 51.5% porosity; (c) effect of sample thickness on α of GF/PDMS composites; and (d) comparison of α between GF/PDMS and GF/CNT/PDMS composites both with 51.5% porosity.

Figure 4 shows the sound absorption coefficients, α , of the GF/PDMS and GF/CNT/PDMS

composites. The GF/PDMS composite with 51.5% porosity presented an excellent α of 0.7 at low frequencies ranging 100-150 Hz, followed by gradual degradation towards the higher frequency end (Figure 4(a)). The overall α increased significantly when the porosity was increased from 9.3% to 51.5% along with reductions in density, which agrees with a recent paper [36]. However, α gradually decreased with a further increase in porosity from 51.5 to 90.8% probably because excessive open pores allowed the sound waves to directly infiltrate into the material: an optimal porosity of 51.5% resulted in the highest sound absorption efficiency of the composites. The benefit of GF on sound damping capability is clearly demonstrated in Figure 4(b). Compared with the neat PDMS foam prepared by etching nickel from the nickel foam/PDMS composite, the GF/PDMS composite with the same porosity displayed a much better sound damping performance. Since no particular functionalization was applied on the GF surface before the coating of PDMS matrix, it is assumed that there were only weak Van der Waals forces between the graphene foam and PDMS as well as between the graphene layers. Therefore, when the sound waves passed into the GF/PDMS composites, their energies were dissipated by sliding between the graphene layers [37] as well as frictions between the graphene and polymer, which effectively contributed to α . At mid-range frequencies 450-800 Hz, the sound absorption capability increased with increasing sample thickness (Figure 4(c)), confirming the previous reports [38, 39].

To fabricate composites with uniformly high sound absorption coefficients over a wider frequency range of 100-1000 Hz, 2 wt.% MWCNTs were introduced into the GF/PDMS composites at an optimized 51.5% porosity to form GF/CNT/PDMS hybrid composites. As shown in Figure 4(d), the incorporation of CNTs significantly extended the applicable frequency band of the composites, achieving a commercially practical α value higher than 0.3 over the whole frequency range, although the peak value was moderately sacrificed. The microscale and nanoscale carbon channels in the composites were responsible for the better performance over 100-1000 Hz, because pores and holes with multiple sizes within the materials are beneficial to broadening the effective frequency band [18]. In addition, the large specific surface area of CNTs further enhanced α by promoting CNT/CNT and CNT/polymer interfacial frictions, due to the creation of extremely large interface areas [40, 41]. As inhomogeneities in the composites, CNTs can also attenuate the sound energy through wave scattering and redirection on the interfaces.

4 CONCLUSIONS

GF/PDMS composites were fabricated by incorporating ethyl acetate-diluted PDMS into the porous GFs. The GF/PDMS composite containing a 90.8% porosity possessed a high electrical conductivity of 6.74 S/cm with an excellent EMI SE of ~25 dB in the X-band frequency. The composite with a 51.5% porosity showed a remarkable sound absorption coefficient of 0.7 at the frequency ranging 100-150 Hz. GF/CNT/PDMS hybrid composites were prepared by introducing well dispersed MWCNTs into the PDMS matrix, which showed significant enhancements in both EMI shielding effectiveness and low-frequency sound absorption, compared to the GF/PDMS composites. The GF/CNT/PDMS composite with 2 wt.% CNTs and 90.8% porosity displayed a remarkable electrical conductivity of 31.5 S/cm and an exceptional EMI SE of ~75 dB, which is equivalent to nearly 200% enhancement against the GF/PDMS composite with the same porosity. The addition of CNTs simultaneously ameliorated the sound energy dissipation by extending the applicable frequency bandwidth of the composites, leading to a commercially viable sound absorption coefficient of more than 0.3 uniformly at 100-1000Hz.

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